

Electrical conductivity of biochar: method optimization and insights from an industrial data set

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Supporting Information

Complete sleeve

Measuring unit sleeve bottom

Area above electrode = sample chamber

Overview individual parts stamp

Mounting measuring system punch

Full stamp

S2 Figure: Black Gauß measurement cell and stamp. Picture taken from (Eurofins Umwelt-Ost, 2023).

S3 Figure: Left: Black Gauß measurement cell installed in the hydraulic press and connected to the multimeter in 4-wire circuit. Right: Reading of distance between sleeve bottom and stamp with a caliper for determination of h_0 (no sample included in measurement cell) and h (sample included in measurement cell) to calculate the height of the compacted biochar pellet.

S4 Table: Parameters for fitting of solid-state electrical conductivities (SEC) of powdered wood or straw biochars produced between 600-800 °C to a restricted exponential model: $SEC = Y_0 + (A - Y_0) \cdot (1 - e^{-K \cdot p})$ with measurement pressure (p) as independent variable. The parameters are valid within a range of p of 31-156 MPa. Biochars were produced on pilot-plant-scale with a residence time of 10 minutes and belong to set A.

Sample	Y_0 [mS cm ⁻¹]	A [mS cm ⁻¹]	K [MPa ⁻¹]	R ²
Wood-600 _{A20}	0.0012	0.0090	0.0050	0.999
Wood-620 _{A21}	0.0066	0.044	0.0060	0.999
Wood-640 _{A22}	0.063	0.41	0.0036	0.998
Wood-660 _{A23}	0.33	1.7	0.010	0.983
Wood-680 _{A24}	2.6	12	0.0099	0.996
Wood-700 _{A25}	10	57	0.0076	0.975
Wood-720 _{A26}	22	130	0.0042	0.994
Wood-740 _{A27}	77	430	0.011	0.992
Wood-760 _{A28}	270	1460	0.0053	0.997
Wood-780 _{A29}	420	2820	0.0069	0.989
Wood-800 _{A30}	810	4320	0.0068	0.986
Sample	Y_0 [mS cm ⁻¹]	A [mS cm ⁻¹]	K [MPa ⁻¹]	R ²
Straw-600 _{A5}	0.1181	0.3382	0.0098	0.999
Straw-620 _{A6}	0.5181	1.5	0.010	0.998
Straw-640 _{A7}	1.1	4.4	0.016	0.999
Straw-660 _{A8}	6.8	26	0.012	0.990
Straw-680 _{A9}	25	76	0.012	0.995
Straw-700 _{A10}	35	120	0.012	0.994
Straw-720 _{A11}	100	330	0.011	0.991
Straw-740 _{A12}	170	590	0.012	0.997
Straw-760 _{A13}	260	860	0.015	0.992
Straw-780 _{A14}	380	1150	0.013	0.982
Straw-800 _{A15}	490	1440	0.016	0.989

S5 Figure: Solid-state electrical conductivity (SEC) of biochars as a function of bulk density of the biochar compact in the measurement cell. Biochars were produced either from wood (a, c, e) or straw (b, d, f) pellets at pyrolysis temperatures between 600-800 °C.

S6 Figure: Particle size sum distribution (Q_3) and particle size density distribution (q_3) of wood biochar produced at 700 °C with 10 minutes residence time and milled with (a) impact mill and 2 mm sieve, (b) mortar and pestle, (c) impact mill with 0.2 mm sieve, and (d) planetary ball mill.

S7 Figure: Particle size sum distribution (Q_3) and particle size density distribution (q_3) of wood biochar produced at 800 °C with 10 minutes residence time and milled with (a) impact mill and 2 mm sieve, (b) mortar and pestle, (c) impact mill with 0.2 mm sieve, and (d) planetary ball mill.

S8 Table: 10th, 50th, and 90th percentile of particle size sum distribution (*d*₁₀, *d*₅₀, and *d*₉₀, respectively) of wood biochar produced at 700 °C with 10 minutes residence time and milled with different milling techniques: Impact mill with either 2 or 0.2 mm installed sieve size, milling with mortar and pestle, and ball milling. Particle size distribution is displayed in S6 Figure.

Milling method	<i>d</i>₁₀ [μm]	<i>d</i>₅₀ [μm]	<i>d</i>₉₀ [μm]
Impact mill (2 mm sieve)	25.4	147.1	398.1
Mortar and pestle	12.6	83.5	258.1
Impact mill (0.2 mm sieve)	4.0	27.7	84.6
Ball mill	1.4	3.7	8.1

S9 Table: 10th, 50th, and 90th percentile of particle size sum distribution (*d*₁₀, *d*₅₀, and *d*₉₀, respectively) of wood biochar produced at 800 °C with 10 minutes residence time and milled with different milling techniques: Impact mill with either 2 or 0.2 mm installed sieve size, milling with mortar and pestle, and ball milling. Particle size distribution is displayed in S6 Figure.

Milling method	<i>d</i>₁₀ [μm]	<i>d</i>₅₀ [μm]	<i>d</i>₉₀ [μm]
Impact mill (2 mm sieve)	21.3	123.4	422.3
Mortar and pestle	10.5	80.0	449.2
Impact mill (0.2 mm sieve)	3.7	25.7	81.7
Ball mill	1.3	3.8	8.8

S10 Table: Parameters for fitting of solid-state electrical conductivity (SEC) of wood biochar produced at 700 °C with 10 minutes residence time to a restricted growth model: $SEC = Y_0 + (A - Y_0) \cdot (1 - e^{-K \cdot d_{50}})$ with 50th percentile of particle size sum distribution (d_{50}) as independent variable. The parameters are valid within a range of d_{50} from 3.73 to 143.5 μm .

Pressure [MPa]	Y_0 [mS cm ⁻¹]	A [mS cm ⁻¹]	K [μm^{-1}]	R ²
31	9	20.	0.041	0.955
62	13	25.	0.10	0.912
94	18	30	0.066	0.992
125	21	32	0.085	0.952
156	23	36	0.062	0.976

S11 Table: Parameters for fitting of solid-state electrical conductivity (SEC) of wood biochar produced at 800 °C with 10 minutes residence time to a restricted growth model: $SEC = Y_0 + (A - Y_0) \cdot (1 - e^{-K \cdot d_{50}})$ with 50th percentile of particle size sum distribution (d_{50}) as independent variable. The parameters are valid within a range of d_{50} from 3.78 to 124.3 μm .

Pressure [MPa]	Y_0 [mS cm ⁻¹]	A [mS cm ⁻¹]	K [μm^{-1}]	R ²
31	970	2510	0.045	0.994
62	1180	3130	0.082	0.995
94	1740	3420	0.084	0.980
125	1280	3860	0.15	0.988
156	2070	4260	0.10	0.940

S12 Figure: Solid-state electrical conductivity corrected for external surface area of biochar particles ($SEC_{corr.}$) of wood biochars produced at 700 °C (a) or 800 °C (b) under 31-156 MPa compaction pressure (samples Wood-700_{C88-91} and Wood-800_{C95-98}) plotted against the 50th percentile of particle size sum distribution (d_{50}) after milling of biochars with different milling techniques, providing decreasing d_{50} values in the following order: impact milling with a 2 mm sieve ($d_{50}=124-143 \mu\text{m}$), mortar and pestle ($d_{50} = 80-83 \mu\text{m}$), impact milling with a 0.2 mm sieve ($d_{50}=26-27 \mu\text{m}$), and ball milling ($d_{50} = 4 \mu\text{m}$). Particle size distributions are presented in S5 and S6 Figures in the Supplementary Material. To account for variations in particle size, the original SEC data (Figure 2 in main text) were multiplied with an external surface increase factor to yield $SEC_{corr.}$. This factor was calculated by assuming spherical particles with a diameter equal to d_{50} . Specifically, the increase factor represents the ratio of the external surface area of a given particle size to that of the largest particle size within each panel.

a

- Impact mill 2mm (d₅₀ = 143 μm)
- Mortar & pestle (d₅₀ = 83 μm)
- ▲ Impact mill 0.2mm (d₅₀ = 27 μm)
- ▼ Ball mill (d₅₀ = 3.7 μm)

b

- Impact mill 2mm (d₅₀ = 124 μm)
- Mortar & pestle (d₅₀ = 80 μm)
- ▲ Impact mill 0.2mm (d₅₀ = 26 μm)
- ▼ Ball mill (d₅₀ = 3.8 μm)

S13 Figure: Solid-state electrical conductivity (SEC) of wood biochars produced at 700 °C (a) or 800 °C (b) plotted against compaction pressure of 31-156 MPa (samples Wood-700_{C88-91} and Wood-800_{C95-98}). Biochars were milled with four different methods which resulted in different particle size distributions. The 50th percentile of particle size sum distribution (d₅₀) is indicated in the legend. Particle size distributions are presented in S6 and S7 Figures in the Supplementary Material.

S14 Table: Prepared mixtures of biochar and inorganic additives. The beech wood biochar was prepared on pilot-plant scale (set B) at 775 °C with 30 minutes residence time. Two different wood ashes obtained from burning chambers processing natural forest wood were used and labelled according to their origin (Möhlin or Gruyère, both Switzerland). In addition, basalt rock powder (Eifelgold Urgesteinsmehl, Lava-Union GmbH, Sinzig, Germany) was used. All mixtures were prepared with a total weight of 1.4 g.

Biochar	Inorganic additive	Proportion of added mineral [%]
Beech wood (775-30)	Möhlin wood ash	0, 15, 20, 25, 30, 40, 60, 80, 100
Beech wood (775-30)	Gruyère wood ash	0, 20, 40, 60, 80, 100
Beech wood (775-30)	Basalt rock powder	0, 20, 40, 60, 80, 100

S15 Figure: Solid-state electrical conductivity (SEC) of biochar mixtures measured under 62 MPa. The figure presents the mixture of a biochar with two different minerals: two wood ashes (Ash 1 and 2, respectively) and rock powder (RP). The biochar was produced from beech wood at 775 °C with 30 minutes residence time and belongs to set B with sample ID 44. The proportion x of each biochar and ash/rock powder in the mixture is given as fraction between 0 to 1. The solid lines represent the fitted linear model to the data with $R^2=0.99$ for Ash 1, $R^2=0.96$ for Ash 2, and $R^2=0.99$ for RP. The origin of the minerals is further described in S12 Table.